

POLITICAL AND CULTURAL ACTIVITIES OF THE TURKESTAN INTELLIGENCE DURING THE EMIGRATION PERIOD

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Annotation: *This article analyzes the political, social, and cultural activities of intellectuals during the period of emigration, who were forced to leave Turkestan due to various political and historical factors in the first half of the 20th century. The article highlights the contributions of the immigrant intelligentsia to preserving the ideas of national independence, conveying the problems of Turkestan to the international community, establishing press and publishing activities abroad, and developing national culture and enlightenment. Their role in promoting the ideas of Turkestan's freedom and national statehood is also scientifically evaluated. It is shown that the activities of the emigrant intelligentsia played an important historical role in preserving the political thinking and cultural heritage of the peoples of Turkestan and passing it on to future generations.*

Keywords: *Turkestan, intelligentsia, emigration, emigration, Jadidism, enlightenment, independence, statehood, press, culture.*

The conquest of Turkestan, first by the Tsarist Empire and then by the Bolsheviks, led thousands of people to a difficult fate called emigration. Each morning presented them with new trials and great mountains to be conquered. But they did not retreat. Behind this endurance, patience, and determination lay a boundless love for Turkestan. According to historians Shodmon Khayitov and Nemat Sobirov, the history of Uzbek migrants can be divided into three periods. These periods are as follows:

- ✓ Uzbek compatriots who left for abroad before the October Revolution of 1917;
- ✓ Compatriots who went abroad in the 1920s and 1930s;
- ✓ Compatriots who participated in battles during World War II and subsequently remained abroad for various reasons. This article is dedicated to the second period.

It is known that Turkestan migrants, even while abroad, fought tirelessly for the freedom of their Motherland. In particular, they published dozens of

magazines such as "Yangi Turkiston," "Milliy Turkiston," "Yosh Turkiston," "Sadoyi muhojirin," and "Turkiston sasi," in which they exposed the evil policy of the Bolsheviks in the homeland. It was from these publications that "Yosh Turkiston" published important information about the horrors of leaving the homeland and the lives of Turkestan emigrants who settled in different countries.

The article "Find out about the condition of those who fled Turkestan and worshipped in Iran," published in No. 48 of "Yosh Turkiston" in 1933, also provides us with important information. It states that tens of thousands of families fled Turkmenistan to seek refuge in Iran, as they had been plundered by the Bolsheviks. They abandoned everything and fled to Iran, thinking only of their own lives. In the article, we read such painful lines: "Their life is very difficult. Hunger, nakedness, and misfortune. It would not be a mistake to say that there is not a single Muslim today who would check on their condition. Is there not even one person who can inform the rulers of the country about this life?" Indeed, the situation of the Turkestanis who fled to Iran as a result of Bolshevik oppression and tyranny was extremely difficult. The article "The Tragedy of the Turkestan Refugees," published in the 29th issue of the same journal in 1932, also supports our opinion. In the introductory part of his article, Mustafa Chukay Efendi notes that the dictatorship of the proletariat established by the Bolsheviks in Turkestan made the lives of the local population unbearable, that as a result of Soviet policy, peaceful and hardworking Turkestanis who had lived by their own labor for centuries found themselves socially, economically, and politically disenfranchised in their native lands, and that control over lands cultivated by the natural labor of the people passed into the hands of the center, while the local population was deprived of the right to use these resources, emphasizing that these actions are a clear manifestation of colonial policy.

Furthermore, the author emphasizes that under Soviet rule, the peoples of Turkestan were deprived not only of political freedom but also of the opportunity to maintain national development and cultural identity; the Soviet central government took full control of local economic resources and severely restricted the population's daily livelihoods, resulting in the systematic suppression and trampling of the people's historical, religious, and spiritual values. According to Mustafa Chukay, due to this vile policy pursued by the Soviet government, Turkestanis were forced to flee to Iran, Turkey, and

Afghanistan, and some of them sacrificed their lives while crossing the Soviet border.

Mustafa Chukai wrote about the difficult situation of the Turkestanis who had moved to Iran: "These days we received information from Iran about the situation of the Turkestanis who had fled there." It is very difficult to describe what life is like for [the Turkestanis] in this country, which has come hoping for peace and a tolerable existence. In order not to wound the silent and sorrowful hearts of the people of Turkestan, we do not recount the lives of our refugees here in detail. Suffice it to say that, according to our information in the form of an anonymous letter, they are "freed from the snow and exposed to the rain" and consider it their greatest happiness to be able to pass under the protection of the Indian government, having lost the last pieces of fabric they managed to take out of their homeland in favor of the Iranian customs authorities...

In Delhi, the "Turkestan Emigrant Union" was established, the main task of which was to unite compatriots scattered throughout India for the sake of the freedom of Turkestan. In particular, in addition to the aforementioned Abdulla Kayumbek, Mahmud Husaynbek Efendi was also an active member of this organization. According to Mustafa Chukay, these two individuals traveled through certain regions of India until June 1934, visited Hyderabad and Bombay, met with Turkestan emigrants living in various cities, and introduced them to the essence of the national liberation movement. Furthermore, they did not limit themselves to Turkestan emigrants, but also met with prominent scholars of India and provided them with information about the current situation in Turkestan and the repressive policy of the Bolsheviks in the region.

According to the 1934 issue of "Yosh Turkiston," the "Turkestan Emigrant Union" purchased a large plot of land on May 21, 1934, in order to provide socio-economic support to Turkestan emigrants in India, and built a building there called "Dorul-muhojirin" (House of Emigrants). In turn, in support of the noble initiative, a group of Turkestan migrants, in particular Abdurahman Efendi, donated 50 rupees, Khoja Azam Efendi 33 rupees, and Khoja Masud Efendi 58 rupees. In addition to vocational training for Turkestanis, great attention was paid to literacy in the House of Emigrants.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the tragedy of Turkestan emigrants, which occurred as a result of Soviet colonial and repressive policy in the 1920s and 1930s, is one of the most painful pages of our national history. The materials presented on the pages of the "Yosh Turkiston" magazine clearly demonstrate

not only the material poverty of the emigrants but also their profound spiritual suffering, loyalty to the motherland, and their selfless struggle for national liberation. Furthermore, the Turkestanis, scattered throughout Iran, India, Turkey, and other countries, sought to preserve their national identity even under the most difficult conditions, honor the memory of the Jadids, and perpetuate the idea of Turkestan's freedom. In this regard, these sources are of great scientific value as important and reliable evidence illuminating the historical significance of the Turkestan emigration movement and its role in the formation of national consciousness and independent thinking.

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